

A Review on Pharmaceutical Process Validation

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Abstract

The process validation is one of the most essential key factor when it comes to the efficient manufacturing of pharmaceutical dosage forms. The process validation assures the highest degree of uniform results and also helps to meet the predefined specifications for the dosage form. Also process validation assures the quality of the product and helps to meet desired results. It basically involves the collection and analyzing the data from product design stage which ensures that the process is capable for the production of quality product. Through this review article we want to have had the knowledge of the process validation and also want to put the basic outline over this process validation process.

Keywords: Pharmaceutical, validation, review.

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Introduction

Process validation is establishing documented evidence which provides a high degree of assurance that a specific process (such as the manufacture of pharmaceutical dosage form) will consistently produce a product meeting its predetermined specifications and quality characteristics. According to FDA, assurance of product quality is derived from careful and systematic attention to a number of important factors, including selection of quality components and materials, adequate product and process design and control of process through in-process and end-product testing.[1]

Need of validation

- Validation gives confident over the product manufacturing process.
- It gives assurance to the product quality as per regulatory requirements.
- Validation is mandatory as per regulatory requirements.

Problems if validation is ignored

- Low process capability.
- Scrap, rework.
- High cost of compliance.
- Risk of drug shortage.
- Releasing poor quality of product.
- Delay in approval of new drugs.
- Quality problems confounding clinical trial data.[2]

Document Regarding Validation

- Getting Started.
- Installation Qualification(IQ).
- Protocol Development.
- Operational Qualification(OQ).
- User Requirements Specifications.
- Performance Qualification(PQ).
- Design Qualification(DQ).[3,4]

Fig 1: Stages of process validation

Planning For Validation

All validation activities should be planned. The key elements of a validation programme should be clearly defined and documented in a validation master plan (VMP) or equivalent documents.

- The VMP should be a summary document which is brief, concise and clear.
- The VMP should contain data on at least the following
 1. Validation policy.
 2. Organizational structure of validation activities.
 3. Summary of facilities, systems, equipment and processes to be validated.
 4. Documentation format: The format to be used for protocols and reports.
 5. Planning and scheduling.
 6. Change control.
 7. Reference to existing document.
 8. Increase of large projects, it may be necessary to create separate validation master plans.^[5]

Types of validation (Fig 1)

1. Prospective validation
2. Concurrent validation
3. Retrospective validation
4. Revalidation (Fig 2)

Prospective Validation

It is defined as the established documented evidence that a system does what it purports to do based on a

pre-planned protocol. This validation carried out prior to distribution either of a new product or a product under a revised manufacturing process. Performed on at least three successive production-sizes.

Concurrent Validation

It is similar to prospective, except that the operating firm will sell the product during the qualification runs, to the public at its market price and also similar to retrospective validation. This validation involves in-process monitoring of critical processing steps and product testing. This helps to generate and documented evidence to show that the production process is in a state of control.

Retrospective Validation

It is defined as the established documented evidence that a system does what it purports to do in review and analysis of historical information. This type of validation of process for a product is already in distribution.

Revalidation

Revalidation provides the evidence that changes in the process and the process environment that are introduced do not adversely affect process characteristics and product quality.^[6]

Fig 2: Validation process

Approach to Process Validation

Process validation is defined as the collection and evaluation of data from the process Design stage through commercial production which establishes scientific that a process is capable of consistently delivering quality product process this validation involves a series of the product and process this guidance describes process validation activities in three stages:-

- Stage 1- Process Design: the commercial manufacturing process is defined during this stage based on knowledge gained through development and scale-up activities.
- Stage 2- Process Qualification: during this stage, the process design is evaluated to determine if the process is capable of reproducible commercial manufacturing.
- Stage 3- Continued Process Verification: ongoing assurance is gained during routine production that the process remains in a state of control.[8]

Process Validation Protocol

1. Protocol approval sheet
2. Table of contents
3. Scope and objective
4. Validation term and responsibility
5. Steps for validation and acceptance criteria
6. Process flow chart
7. Procedure

8. For review of raw material/packing material
9. Evaluation of active raw material
10. Qualification of equipment
11. Test instrument calibration
12. Revalidation criteria
13. Reference document
14. Product detail
15. Raw material for bulk manufacturing and their function
16. Equipment detail
17. Packing material detail
18. Manufacturing process flow chart
19. Critical process parameters
20. In-process specification
21. Sampling procedure and testing plan
22. Change control
23. Deviations
24. Stability
25. Incidence
26. Conclusion
27. Report and approval. [9]
- 28.

Advantages of process validation

- It is simple process and moisture sensitive and heat sensitive products can also be processed.
- Expanded real time monitoring and adjustment of process.
- Decreases the risk of preventing problems and thus assure the smooth running of the process.

- Enhanced ability to statistically evaluate process performance and product variables e.g. individuals; mean; range; control limits.
- Enhanced data and evaluation capabilities and increased confidence about process reproducibility and product quality.
- Improved ability to set target parameters and control limits for routine production, correlating with validation results.
- Enhanced reporting capability.[10,11]

Conclusion

It is clear from the above study that the process validation is one of the most crucial and most needed step if one wants to develop the quality product. The process validation have the series of steps that must be adopted during the development lifecycle of the product. Also once the product is developed its process validation is done in order to identify that the product so generated should meet all the pre- defined specifications and also to detect that the product should be developed under controlled supervision. Also the process validation control is more important in order to make the product to meet the desired outcomes and so have the better strength, purity and stability. Also the process validation provides consistency and reliability to the industry for drug development.

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